

THE ROLE OF CONCEPTS OF CONTRADICTIONS IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article describes new approaches aimed at teaching students to think realistically and form their creative activities by means of the concepts of contradiction.

Key words: contradictions, primary education, creative activity, literary forms and images, mathematics, physics, morality, chemistry.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada qarama-qarshilik tushunchalari vositasida o'quvchilarni real fikrlashga o'rgatish va ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirishga qaratilgan yangicha yondashuvlar bayon etilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: qarama-qarshiliklar, boshlang'ich ta'lim, ijodiy faoliyat, Adabiy shakl va obrazlar, matematika, fizika, ahloq, kimyo.

Аннотация: В статье описаны новые подходы, направленные на обучение студентов реалистическому мышлению и формированию своей творческой деятельности посредством понятий противоречия.

Ключевые слова: противоречия, начальное образование, творческая деятельность, литературные формы и образы, математика, физика, нравственность, химия.

First of all, favorable organizational and legal conditions have been created in our country to raise a mature generation. President Sh.Mirziyoyev's reforms in this field have been consistently continued, the work being done on the development of educational institutions based on the requirements and standards of the present time, the attention paid to the growth of our future owners as well as the worthy successors of our great ancestors. I have the noble goal of ensuring that they grow up.

Today, our country is taking a bold step on its own path of economic and socio-cultural development. Deep changes in this direction are rapidly entering all areas, and this, in turn, has created the need for fundamental reforms in the education system, because education improves the internal capabilities and abilities of the growing young generation. along with the emergence, it is also the main source of the implementation of the national program of personnel training. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, where great reforms are being implemented, the existence of independent and creative thinking young people is the need of the times, because only people with a personal worldview will be able to achieve success that ensures the development of society.

The above opinion encourages all teachers in the education system to be mature, knowledgeable and inquisitive in all aspects. In particular, the primary teacher, who creates the foundation of education, must be mature and perfect in all aspects. The reason is that today's children are very ambitious, curious and intelligent, and they are completely different from the children before them. Today's children with their intelligence and intelligence sometimes make the class teacher think and surprise. From elementary school, children have different ways of thinking, different approaches, and personal thinking in relation to situations, which are growing day by day. . Let's talk a little about the concepts of opposites together.

The ideas of opposites are creation, change, development, decay, destruction, extinction, etc. anything and everything directly or indirectly covers our entire information space, including science, philosophy, religion, language, morality, ethics, art, mass media, etc. We will give examples of this from several characteristic sciences.

Mathematics - plus - minus, integration - differentiation, two parts of a mathematical equation, multiplication - division, addition - subtraction.

Physics - plus and minus charges, gravity - repulsion, motion - reaction, charge - discharge, dissipation - concentration, increase and decrease of entropy.

Chemistry - oxidation - reduction, reversible and irreversible reactions, release and absorption of heat.

Biology - birth - death, development - degradation of the body, male - female, assimilation - dissimilation.

Philosophy - matter - consciousness, object - subject, yin and yang, dialectic, absolute - relative.

Logic - contradictions, thesis - antithesis.

Religion: polar gods [1,2,3], God - Satan, Allah - Satan, good and evil spirits, heaven - hell, saint - sinner.

Language: the structure of a grammatical sentence (subject - object, situation) [4]. Words - interaction, relationship, empathy, cooperation ...

Morality: good - bad, good - bad.

General scientific field: induction - deduction, analysis - synthesis.

Politics: power - opposition, elections - distribution.

Sports: two teams (football, hockey...), two rivals (chess, boxing...).

Movies: Stirlitz - Muller, Wolf and Rabbit, Tom and Jerry.

Literary forms and images: "War and Peace", "Crime and Punishment", "Fathers and Sons", "The Prince and the Pauper", "Brightness and Poverty", "Courage and Love", "Love and Hate", "Love and Separation...", happiness - unhappiness, joy - trouble, friend - enemy, evil detective - good detective, victory - defeat, beginning - end, black and white, "goes left - the song begins, to the right - he says. fairy tale ...", Sherlock Holmes - prof. Moriarty, physicists - lyrics, etc. Even the Karamazov brothers were presented by F. Dostoyevsky as typical opposites. General case: any pair of words (and their content after them), one of which repeats the other with the addition of the prefix - not, anti -, but -, against -, different -, etc., and in all cases, without exception, the existence of all contradictions is the source of various processes in physical, chemical, biological, political and other systems, and is the engine of the development of the plot, the intrigue of the scenario, the core. the struggle of rivals and, as a result, corresponding significant changes in the initial state of the overall system. Examples of religious and mythical contrasts that create the world are particularly impressive: pure and impure forces in the mythology of the ancient Slavs and ideas of modern Christians and Muslims [1], polar gods from

ancient Indonesian myths [2], double and impure forces. Sumerian tripartite gods [3], Ranga and papa (earth and sky) in ancient Indian myths, symbol of the Great Frontier of Tai Chi in ancient China, Uranus - Gaia (sky and earth) among the ancient Greeks, dual gods. The Trinity of the Mayan Calendar and more.

Many of these contradictions arose in the era when not only science but also writing existed. And if you believe these myths, the concept of opposites appeared when not only man, but also the world itself existed. And if you don't believe it, it happened at the beginning of our civilization, i.e. was one of the cornerstones of our outlook and the process of knowing the world. Since all these ideas appear independently of each other everywhere (in the world), always and even in all-round, diverse and universal forms, they represent some universal, deep, fundamental laws of the world through our worldview. is clear to reflect. mind Therefore, when studying any object or process of the surrounding world, we have the right to expect the manifestation of the action of these laws. Thus, contradictions can be put at the basis of the methodology of description and study of any objects and processes, and in general, an inseparable pair or several inseparable opposites can be elevated to the status of the principle of opposites. That is why, from Lao Tzu and Heraclitus to Hegel and dialectical materialism, the concept of opposites has played a very important role in many philosophical and worldview systems. In particular, the concept of "contradictions" and their "struggle" is the basis of the watershed between metaphysics and dialectics. The role of contradictions was declared to be fundamental and universal, then it was criticized, revised, modernized, faced with changes in interpretation and interpretation, it was overthrown from the position of a secondary attribute of knowledge, to completely abandon its use. to attempts. . The last attempt, as you know, belongs to modern postmodernists from philosophy (Foucault). A large number of specific types of conflict have been proposed, as well as many different classifications.

This topic is well represented in domestic and foreign literature at all levels, from original articles and monographs to encyclopedias, dictionaries and textbooks. Its rich history of many thousands of years is covered by Lao Tzu, Confucius,

Heraclitus, Pythagoras, Socrates, Plato, Empedocles, Aristotle, R. Descartes, B. Spinoza, G. Leibniz, I. Kant, N. Kuzansky, G. Hegel, R. Schelling, F. Engels, V. Solovyov, K. Barth, R. Bultman, E. Thurneizer, K. Popper and others.

It is very characteristic that each of the above-mentioned philosophers understood the principle of contradiction in their own way, depending on their worldview, philosophical and religious position. But in this history of the principle of contradictions, one important aspect draws attention, namely: the clear difference between the existing philosophical ideas and interpretations of the principle of contradictions from the richest empirical base of natural science (in particular, modern) and, accordingly, in the development of natural science, the extremely insignificant role of this principle in revealing its laws and changing scientific paradigms. It is this situation that ultimately led natural scientists, especially physicists, astronomers, and cosmologists to lose interest not only in dialectics, but also in philosophy as a whole.

Not only the interest, but also the reputation and status of philosophy is declining. Many discoveries are made not because of philosophical dogmas, but in spite of them. Philosophy is not obliged to predict the possible development of a particular science, but tries to somehow explain and explain the discoveries of modern cosmogony, physics, astrophysics, archeology, paleontology, biology, genetics, psychology, religion and other "ideological" sciences.

There can be many reasons for this situation, and in our opinion, the main ones are as follows.

1. Self-separation of philosophy from natural science, turning it into a special professional language, a special club of a high intellectual elite with its own problems, distant from the problems of natural science and society in general, 'often outright neglect. "technologists" and scientific "plumbers" (M. Mamardashvili), philosophers, of course, do not include themselves.
2. Definition of philosophy not as a methodological basis for the development of applied sciences and natural sciences in general, but as a coherent, logical and beautiful art of philosophizing.

3. The obvious inertia and dogmatism of many philosophical concepts and theories and, as a result, their lack of connection with the empirical basis of natural science. According to K. Popper, this is "iron-concrete dogmatism" (the definition refers to dialectical materialism, in which, according to K. Popper, dialectics denies itself).
4. Inadequate level of generalization of applied concepts.
5. Lack of clarity, precision and completeness (sufficiency and necessity of content) of the concepts used in describing one or another forms of conflict. First of all, concepts such as struggle, enmity, conflict, opposition, elimination of conflict or opposition ("love" Empedocles), unity. Their content, interpretation and understanding are infinitely wide, depending on the field of their application and the position of the author of the study.
6. Inadequate development of the concept of "opposition". Dispersion, vagueness, diversity of the concept of conflict, and at the same time the narrowness of individual definitions. Contrasts, as a rule, are determined by formal, external features that have nothing to do with their composition, structure, possible functions and types of interaction. There is no generally accepted definition of the concept of "contradictions". Hence, complete arbitrariness in the definition, application and interpretation of research results is inevitable.
7. In the present context, the principle of opposites has all the hallmarks of a problem that is misplaced and, accordingly, solved.

With the further development of the principle of contradiction in one of the modern methodological and worldview concepts, which is called closed system theory, the last five reasons were eliminated to some extent [4,5].

In this theory, it is accepted that oppositions can be represented in the simplest (elementary) version as a closed system of object and object. In the complex version, opposites are expressed as an object and two or more opposite objects, which also form a closed system (in an abstract ideal, a completely closed system). The latter is defined as the object's environment by an infinite complication of a set of other objects opposite to the object under study. A set of objects and environments that oppose an object is defined as a generalized anti-object. The object itself has only

one indicator - the state defined as the ability to change the generalized anti-object that the object forms a closed system. In this theory, the object, the generalized anti-object, their states and the interconnected set of other concepts necessary for learning based on the preliminary definitions of the closed system connecting them and their interrelationship was also developed. In particular, the general state conservation law of all interacting parts of one closed system is established. This conceptual apparatus and its interrelationships are closely related to the system of generalized physical parameters listed among the corresponding physical applications of the theory [4,5].

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